

Enhancing EFL Learners' English Writing Skills through a Genre-based Approach

Xiumei Hu and Adam Steinhoff¹

The University of Sydney

ABSTRACT

A genre-based approach (GBA) to teaching writing is used in both English as a second and foreign language (ESL/EFL) contexts. The paper discusses a GBA's pedagogical applications and theoretical background before reviewing previous GBA-related research. Following this, the three lesson plans are presented. Lesson Plans 1 and 2 focus on email writing to recommend a job, while Lesson Plan 3 is focused on recipe writing. The article also provides guidelines to assist teachers in using the lesson plans before concluding with a brief section on the limitations of a GBA in teaching writing.

Keywords: Genre-based approach, lesson plan, TESOL, writing

INTRODUCTION

A GBA to writing offers teachers an additional approach to writing instruction in the language learning classroom. A GBA places greater emphasis on writing for specific purposes, thus making it more applicable to real-life situations. However, according to Hao and Sivell (2002), test preparation can often be a priority in EFL contexts in China. Thus, teachers may assign written tasks deemed fit for this purpose, such as essays, rather than authentic forms of communication, such as letters or emails, resumes, or subject-specific assignments. Although this practice

¹ Address for correspondence: huxiumei0306@163.com; adam.steinhoff@sydney.edu.au

may be effective for exam preparation, it can be problematic for overall writing development as, according to Widodo (2006), even after dedicating years to the development of writing skills, EFL learners, in general, still find writing to be the most challenging skill to master. In light of this, we encourage its use in language learning classrooms in general and specifically as an approach in EFL classrooms in junior high schools in China. Hence, the lesson plans presented in this article have been designed with a particular group of public junior high school students in China in mind, where English is a compulsory subject. Based on the CEFR, the language proficiency level of the students can be said to be B2. The class consists of approximately 40 students with an equal mix of male and female students.

This paper discusses pedagogical implications, the theoretical background to a GBA, and previous GBA-related research. Following this, Lesson Plans 1 and 2 are presented, which aim to teach students the fundamental structure of an email, expose them to linguistic elements and sentence structures related to job recommendations, and provide them with the opportunity to engage in independent email writing to recommend a job to a friend. Furthermore, Lesson Plan 3 aims to teach students how to write a recipe. These lesson plans are supported by guidelines to assist teachers in their use, and a brief section on the limitations of a GBA in teaching writing follows this section.

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES

The development stage of the genre-based approach

The genre-based theory is rooted in the systemic functional linguistics of Michael Halliday (1994), and it was further developed by Martin (1999a, 1999b) and Rothery (1996) – two prominent scholars during the early stage of systemic functional genre analysis (Paltridge, 2014). Martin and Rothery doubted the ability of progressivism in English teaching to benefit working-class students and instead believed that it would favour middle-class students (Whittaker et al., 2006). Similarly, genre theorists from the Sydney School advocated the use of genre theory and pedagogy for students whose ‘voice is closest to the literate culture of power in industrial societies’ (Whittaker et al., 2006) to tackle this language-related inequality and solve the literacy needs of students (Christie & Martin, 1997; White et al., 2015). Over time, genre pedagogy has become increasingly common in second language (L2) writing courses as a result of communicative approaches and due to increased comprehension of literacy (Hyland, 2004b).

Theoretical framework of the genre-based approach

The theoretical framework of the genre-based approach has five stages. These stages include (1) building the context, (2) modelling and deconstructing the text, (3) joint construction of the text, (4) independent construction of the text, and (5) linking related texts. These stages are explained below.

Figure 1. The stages of a genre-based approach (Feez, 1998)

First, building the context emphasises the importance of understanding the background and meaning of texts before engaging in writing. During this stage, teachers seek to gain a greater awareness of learners' life experiences to enhance their comprehension. Second, modelling and deconstructing the text involves encouraging students to analyse how the events are arranged in the model texts and to identify the structural and linguistic characteristics employed. Engaging in discussions regarding these aspects further enhances their understanding. Third, joint construction of the text refers to students collaborating in group projects, responding to guided inquiries, gathering information, and reconstructing, for example, a recount or story based on the model texts. Fourth, in the next stage – independent construction of the text – students are expected to produce their writing text independently, with teachers assisting only when necessary. Finally, linking related texts encourages students to compare what they have learned with different genres, thus aiding their comprehension of how genres are used to achieve specific goals. This comparative analysis enhances their overall understanding of genre-based writing.

Review of previous empirical research on the genre-based approach

To assess the effectiveness of a GBA in teaching writing, scholars (e.g., Abdel-Malek, 2020; Dyson, 2016; Mingsakoon & Srinon, 2018; Nagao, 2022; Wicaksono et al., 2022) have conducted empirical research to investigate its impact on students' writing performance and skills. Wicaksono et al. (2022) found that using the GBA facilitated students' text creation and ability to achieve success. Similarly, Dyson (2016) found that when comparing a GBA with an alternate approach used in an EAP program, the GBA was superior in overall performance.

Other researchers (e.g., Abdel-Malek, 2020; Mingsakoon & Srinon, 2018; Nagao, 2022) have explored using the genre-based approach to improve students' writing performance in various contexts. Mingsakoon and Srinon (2018) showed that a GBA enhanced Thai EFL upper secondary school students' comprehension and writing skills in recounts. Additionally, Abdel-Malek (2020) found that a GBA empowered Arabic students to expand their linguistic repertoire in addressing the sociocultural purpose of recounts of habitual events. Nagao (2022) employed a GBA to instruct Japanese EFL university students in descriptive report writing and found that both low- and high-proficiency EFL students demonstrated enhanced comprehension of essays. However, they derived benefits from distinct aspects. In China, Deng et al. (2014) demonstrated that genre-based training could improve students' genre awareness, while Cai (2016), in exploring the effectiveness of a GBA in teaching and learning academic lexical phrases, found that employing an integrated GBA effectively assisted master's students' acquisition of this language feature. Finally, He (2022) found that implementing a GBA could enhance persuasive skills in advertisement writing among college students.

Challenges exist around the implementation and instruction of a GBA. Regarding the former, research is needed to address (1) teachers' concerns around their limitations in understanding the fundamental principles of a GBA and (2) how to find suitable material relevant to students' lived experiences (Shi, 2015; Syafitri, 2018). Regarding the latter, research should focus on providing sufficient detail around the generic structure of written texts during writing instruction (Liu & Chen, 2022; Shi, 2015).

AN INTRODUCTION TO THE THREE LESSON PLANS

The three lesson plans presented below are designed as part of a broader EFL syllabus in a high school context in China (15–18-year-old students), which aims to

develop students' writing skills in authentic situations. Lesson Plans 1 and 2 are designed to teach students how to write an email to recommend a job to a friend. In doing so, students learn certain conventions of email writing while gaining an awareness of the specific functional language and content used in emails written with a purpose to recommend. Lesson Plan 3 is designed to promote familiarity with reading recipes while also developing writing skills in creating a recipe. Since these students may be travelling overseas in the future, the skill of reading recipes and subsequently cooking the dish in question is considered necessary, and it is argued that writing a recipe through a GBA will enhance their understanding of the different parts of a recipe.

The learning outcomes that relate to these lesson plans are that students will learn (1) the conventions of writing an email, (2) the content and functional language related to writing an email to recommend a job to a friend, and (3) vocabulary and functional language (e.g., imperatives) used in writing a recipe. Other skills that will be developed through these lesson plans are (1) critical thinking skills, (2) interactive skills through group work, and (3) making links between the content of the writing tasks and prior knowledge.

LESSON PLANS

The following three lesson plans have been designed for teaching 15-18-year-old high school students in China. The lesson plans are divided into three parts: (1) lesson procedures, (2) what the teacher will do, and (3) what the students will do, thus providing teachers with a snapshot of what the teacher and students will be doing at any one time. Regarding the lesson procedures, three stages will be delivered in one class due to the duration of a given class in high school. The number of steps in each stage may differ depending on the aim of the stage.

Figure 2 presents Lesson Plan 1, which aims to teach students how to write an email to recommend a job to their friends.

Lesson Plan 1		
<p><i>Topic:</i> To write an email to recommend a job <i>Time:</i> 50 minutes <i>Grouping:</i> 4 groups <i>Material:</i> four phones, handouts, a job-search website <i>Objectives:</i> To learn the structure of an email. To learn job-related lexis. To practice writing an email.</p>		
Lesson Procedures	What the teacher will do	What the students will do
Building the context (10 minutes)		
Step 1: Establish links to students' prior experience	Ask the following questions: What kind of job do you want to do in the future? What do you consider important when applying for a job (e.g., salary, working time, etc.)?	In groups, discuss these questions.
Step 2: Build the relevant contextual background	The teacher uses authentic materials where possible: Open the job search websites to show how to use the job website (see Appendix 1). Ask students to interview one student in their groups about their favourite job and then search for this job on the job website to finish the task (see Appendix 2).	Complete Handout 1 (see Appendix 2).
<p><i>Note:</i> Before the class, the teacher distributed four smartphones to the groups and signed them up for the job website.</p>		

Figure 2 Lesson Plan 1

Modelling and deconstructing the text (20 minutes)		
Step 1: Model text	Provide students with the sample text (see Appendix 3). Ask students to identify the genre and discuss the structure of the text.	Discuss in pairs. Choose one person as a representative to answer the class report.
Step 2: Deconstruct the email structure	Analyse the structure and identify the main features of the email (see Appendix 4).	Participate in the whole-class activity.
Step 3: Deconstruct the content of the sample text	Distribute Handout 2 (see Appendix 5)	Please read the email and answer the questions (see Appendix 5) by discussing them in groups.
Joint Construction (20 minutes)		
Step 1: Matching activity	Distribute the matching activity to the students (see Appendix 6)	Students finish the matching in groups.
Step 2: Reassembly exercise	The teacher asks the students to answer the following questions while reading the model text: What kinds of verbs or modal verbs are used in this text? Circle these modal verbs. Finish Handout 3 (see Appendix 7).	In groups, students circle the modal verbs in the text (see Appendix 7).
Step 3: Joint construction of the text	Instruct students to: Choose a job in their groups. Collaborate to write a job recommendation for another group. Follow the structure of Handout 4 (see Appendix 8)	In groups, students complete Handout 4 (see Appendix 8).

Figure 2 Lesson Plan 1 (continued)

Figure 3 presents Lesson Plan 2, which focuses students on the actual independent writing of the email to recommend a job to their friend.

Lesson Plan 2		
<i>Topic:</i> Learn how to write an email to recommend a job to your friends		
<i>Time:</i> 40 minutes		
<i>Objectives:</i>		
To write an individual email to recommend a job to a friend.		
To learn the specific features to be included in an email.		
Lesson Procedures	What the teacher will do	What the students will do
Independent construction (30 minutes)		
Step 1: Review	Guide students in reviewing an email's structure and job recommendations' content.	Review specific handouts and materials used in previous lessons on the structure of an email.
Step 2: Independent construction	Give students the writing topic: Write an email recommending a job to your partner based on the interview content in handout 1.	Students are given 25 minutes to complete the writing task. Students can use the sentence structure they learned from the sample text.
Step 3: Provide help	Monitor students and provide support if needed.	Students write their respective emails.
Linking related texts (10 minutes)		
Step 1: Reflection	Ask students to reflect on the following: What is the function of an email?	In pairs, students discuss this question and summarise the key points.
Step 2: Comparing	Provide students with several other emails to summarise the key points of an email (see Appendix 9).	

Figure 3 Lesson Plan 2

Figure 4 presents Lesson Plan 3, which aims to teach how to write a recipe. The content for this lesson comes from an authentic cookbook. Given the simplistic

nature of the model text for this lesson plan (i.e., ingredients and instructions), the five stages of the GBA can be completed in one lesson.

Lesson Plan 3		
<p><i>Topic:</i> To learn how to write a recipe <i>Time:</i> 50 minutes <i>Grouping:</i> 4 groups <i>Materials:</i> Dictionaries and a bowl of salad <i>Objectives:</i> To learn specific vocabulary and phrases about recipes. To know the conventions of a recipe. To practice writing a recipe.</p>		
Lesson Procedures	What the teacher will do	What the students will do
Building a context (5 minutes)		
Step 1: Lead in	Show students a bowl of salad and ask the following question: How many ingredients can you see in this bowl?	Think, pair, share. Different students from each pair answer the question.
Step 2: Link to prior knowledge and build related knowledge	Ask the students: Imagine you are making a salad. Write down the ingredients you want to include.	In groups, discuss this question. One person in the group writes down the ingredients for the salad (see Appendix 10, Handout 5).
Modelling and deconstructing the text (10 minutes)		
Step 1: Model text	Show students a model text of a salad recipe (see Appendix 11).	
Step 2: Deconstructing the structure	Ask students to discuss the following: What textual features should be included in a recipe? Ask students to complete the matching activity based on the structure of this text.	Finish the matching activity for the recipe text (see Appendix 12).

Figure 4: Lesson Plan 3

Step 3: Deconstructing the context	Ask students to categorise the ingredients by bowl and platter and fill in the blanks (see Appendix 13, Handout 6).	In pairs, students complete Handout 6.
<i>Note: Since this recipe is from authentic material, some words are difficult for students at this level. Students are advised to bring their dictionaries to the class.</i>		
Joint Construction (15 minutes)		
Step 1: Circle keywords	Ask students to circle the verbs and verb phrases in the text. Encourage students to use a dictionary to check unfamiliar vocabulary.	In groups, students circle the verbs and verb phrases in the recipe text.
Step 2: Reassembly exercise	Ask students to select the correct verbs to complete the flow chart according to the sample text (see Appendix 14).	In groups, students complete Handout 7.
Step 3: Joint construction	Ask each group to choose a particular type of salad that they would like to make. Ask groups to write a recipe for their chosen salad. Encourage students to use the verbs and verb phrases learned in Step 2.	In groups, students collaborate to write a salad recipe using the verbs and verb phrases learned in Step 2.
Independent construction (15 minutes)		
Step 1: Independent construction	Assign the following 15-minute individual writing task: Write a salad recipe. Please encourage students to use the verbs and sentences they learned before.	Students write their recipes.

Figure 4: Lesson Plan 3 (continued)

Step 2: Monitor	Monitor the students and provide help if necessary.	
Linking related texts (5 minutes)		
Step 1: Reflection	Guide students in reflecting on the following question: What is the purpose of a recipe?	In pairs, students discuss this question.
Step 2: Comparing	Provide students with other recipes to identify and summarise commonalities (see Appendix 15). Elicit ideas from students.	As a whole-class discussion, students provide ideas.

Figure 4: Lesson Plan 3 (continued)

HOW TO APPLY THESE LESSON PLANS

Guidelines for teachers

Teachers can consider the following guidelines when using these three lesson plans.

Lesson Plan 1

- Check the job-search website in advance to ensure that students will be able to log on successfully.
- Ensure all materials are prepared before class.
- During Step 2, teachers should specify the time available (i.e., 7 minutes) for job searching to prevent excessive time spent on this step.
- The primary purpose of Step 2 is to help students to know the modal verbs used to express the job requirements. Teachers can also use other activities to achieve this goal.

Lesson Plan 2

- In the beginning, teachers should guide students in reviewing what they have learned in the previous class to help students transition more smoothly into independent writing.
- During the independent stage, teachers should only offer assistance when needed, and students should be reminded to finish their tasks within the given time.

Lesson Plan 3

- The recipe contains some difficult words. Before class, teachers should tell students to bring a dictionary. In Step 1 of modelling and deconstructing the text, teachers can choose one authentic recipe from other sources, but they should ensure that this recipe is suitable for students' language level.
- During the joint construction stage (*Steps 1 and 2*), the grammar in a recipe is typically not complicated, so the teacher should emphasise the recipe's vocabulary and procedural aspects.
- During the same stage (*Step 3*), students may have different opinions about what kinds of salad and ingredients they will use. If students struggle to agree, teachers should assist in the decision-making process.

LIMITATIONS OF GBA FOR DESIGNING LESSON PLANS

As we have developed these lesson plans, we recognise some potential limitations of a GBA in terms of the potential for decontextualisation in the classroom, unintentionally stifling creativity through the provision of samples, and focusing on a formula for writing rather than focusing on the purpose of writing. Teachers need to be mindful of the importance of creating a context in the classroom that allows the students to immerse themselves in the genre. Related to this, Lave and Wenger (1991) argue that genres are too tricky and diverse to be extracted from their contexts and taught in educational settings. Furthermore, in the name of promoting student creativity, teachers should be aware that the provision of samples in the writing process could lend itself to limiting expression. Hyland (2004b) contends that the presence of samples within the GBA may impose constraints that limit the creative potential of individual writers. Finally, teachers

also need to be mindful of the importance of emphasising the purpose of the written text and refrain from approaching instruction from a formulaic standpoint that needs to be taught as part of the curriculum. Related to this, Derewianka (2015) argues that, in the classroom setting, genres are usually taught merely as items to be included in the curriculum, focusing on following a set formula rather than beginning with the underlying purpose of a task. In light of the above possible limitations, teachers need to be mindful of these when applying lesson plans.

CONCLUSION

Based on an understanding of a GBA, this paper was undertaken to design three lesson plans to improve the writing performance of Chinese students in EFL classes. These three lesson plans followed the five steps of the teaching-learning cycle to develop the learning material. Drawing from this process, it is suggested that a GBA effectively addresses writing difficulties in EFL classrooms. One of the primary reasons for its effectiveness is that students can learn the text's language features and social functions and how to apply this approach to subsequent writing tasks. Therefore, it is recommended that teachers incorporate this approach into their writing classes. Teachers can make necessary adjustments based on their circumstances to ensure successful implementation in diverse classrooms.

AUTHORS

Xiumei Hu completed the Master of Education (TESOL) at The University. Her interests include English language syllabus design, Genre-based applications, and second language writing.

Adam Steinhoff is a PhD candidate in TESOL at The University of Sydney. His research interests are in the areas of academic writing, dynamic assessment, second language acquisition. He also teaches the Master of Education (TESOL) at The University of Sydney.

REFERENCES

- Abdel-Malek, M. (2020). Empowering Arabic learners to make meaning: A genre-based approach. *System*, 94, 1-11.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2020.102329>

- Cai, (Luna) Jing. (2016). An exploratory study on an integrated genre-based approach for the instruction of academic lexical phrases. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 24, 58–74.
- Christie, F., & Martin, J. R. (1997). *Genres and institutions: Social processes in the workplace and school*. Continuum.
- Dyson, B. P. (2016). EAP or genre-based? A comparison of two curricular approaches to the preparation of international students for university. *University of Sydney Papers in TESOL*, 11, 31–66.
- Deng, L., Chen, Q., & Zhang, Y. (2014). Fostering Chinese EFL learners' genre awareness: A Genre-based approach. In *Developing Chinese EFL learners' generic competence* (pp. 17–29). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-54845-1_3
- Derewianka, B. (2015). The contribution of genre theory to literacy education in Australia. In J. Turbill, G. Barton & C. Brock (Eds.), *Teaching writing in today's classrooms: Looking back to looking forward* (pp. 69–86). Australian Literary Educators' Association.
- Feez, S. (1998). *Text-based syllabus design*. Sydney, Australia: Macquarie University.
- Hao, X., & Sivell, J. (2002). Integrating reading and writing in EFL composition in China. *The Annual Meeting of the Canadian Association of Applied Linguistics*, 468–499.
- He, Y. (2022). Using genre-based approach to teach persuasive netvertisement for English learners in a Chinese vocational college. *Arab World English Journal*, 13(1), 173–195. <https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol13no1.12>
- Hyland, K. (2004b). *Genre and second language writing*. University of Michigan Press.
- Halliday, M.A.K (1994). *An introduction to functional grammar*. Edward Arnold.
- Lave, J., and E. Wenger (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.

- Liu, C., & Chen, M. (2022). A genre-based approach in the secondary school English writing class: Voices from student-teachers in the teaching practicum. *Frontiers in Psychology, 13*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.992360>
- Martin, J. R. (1999a). Linguistics and the consumer: Theory in practice. *Linguistics and Education, 9*, 409–446.
- Martin, J. R. (1999b). Mentoring semogenesis: 'Genre-based' literacy pedagogy. In F. Christie (Ed.), *Pedagogy and the shaping of consciousness: Linguistic and social processes* (pp. 123–155). Cassell.
- Mingsakoon, P., & Srinon, U. (2018). Development of secondary school students' generic structure execution in personal experience recount writing texts through SFL genre-based approach. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies, 9*(6), 112–119. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.all.v.9n.6p.112>
- Nagao, A. (2022). A Genre-based approach to teaching descriptive report writing to Japanese EFL university students. *TESL-EJ (Berkeley, Calif.), 26*(3). <https://doi.org/10.55593/ej.26103a13>
- Paltridge, B. (2014). Genre and second-language academic writing. *Language Teaching, 47*(3), 303–318.
- Rothery, J. (1996). Making changes: Developing an educational linguistics. In R. Hasan & G. Williams (Eds.), *Literacy in society* (pp. 86–123). Longman
- Shi, L. S. (2015). *Chinese EFL teachers' cognition about the potential of SFL genre-based pedagogy for teaching College English writing: A case study at a university in China* (Doctoral dissertation), Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Wollongong. <http://ro.uow.edu.au/theses/4722>
- Syafitri, W. (2018). The implementation of genre-based approach in teaching writing at SMA 4 Solok. *Journal Polingua: Scientific Journal of Linguistic, Literature and Education, 5*(2), 60–66. <https://doi.org/10.30630/polingua.v5i2.39>
- White, P. R. R., Mammone, G., & Caldwell, D. (2015). Linguistically based inequality, multilingual education and a genre-based literacy development pedagogy: insights from the Australian experience. *Language and Education, 29*(3), 256–271. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2014.994527>

Whittaker, R., McCabe, A., & O'Donnell, M. (2006). *Language and literacy: Functional approaches*. Bloomsbury Publishing.

Wicaksono, F. A., Sulistyarningsih, S., & Syakur, A. (2022). A genre-based approach to improve the students' writing skills. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 6(3), 3391-3397.

Widodo, H. (2006). Designing a genre-based lesson plan for an academic writing course. *English Teaching*, 5(3), 173-199.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: The job search website

The screenshot displays the LinkedIn Jobs interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Search by title, skill, or company" and navigation icons for Home, My Network, Jobs, and Messaging. On the left side, a vertical menu contains options: My jobs, Job alerts, Demonstrate skills, Interview prep, Resume Builder, Job seeker guidance, and Application settings, along with a "Post a free job" button. The main content area is divided into two sections. The first section, "Suggested job searches", features a row of search filters: marketing manager, hr, legal, sales, and amazon, with a second row containing google and analyst. The second section, "Recommended for you", is based on the user's profile and search history. It lists two job opportunities: "English and Art Teacher" by Teacher Bay in Shanghai, China (On-site), posted 3 weeks ago with an "Easy Apply" button; and "University full-time English Oral teachers" by Shanghai Bowai Education in Shanghai, China, which is actively recruiting, promoted, and has 21 applicants, also featuring an "Easy Apply" button.

Appendix 2: Handout 1

Your partner will use a job website to find a job that interests him/her. Interview your partner to complete the table below.

Name of Interviewee	
Job	
Salary	
Location	
Required skills	
Working hours	

Appendix 3: Model email (1)

To: erik1221@cup.org
 From: ingrid_soljberg@cup.org
 Subject: IT'S MUM – LOOK AT THIS JOB!

Erik,

I've found a great job for you. It's in Oslo and I know you want to live there. Here's the link: www.itcompany42.org/jobs I know this **company**.

The job is for a software³ **engineer**. They pay £4,150 per month!

You must have studied Computer Science at university, and you have to have two years' experience. It also says that you must know some Norwegian. You don't have to speak Norwegian a lot, so it's OK for you.

Let me know what you think!

Love,
Mum

Appendix 4: The main features of an email**Appendix 5: Handout 2**

The email to Erik is a job named _____

The pay for Erik's job is _____

Where is the job location? _____

What kinds of requirements are for this job? _____

Why does his mum recommend this job to him? _____

Appendix 6: Matching Activity

Subject	Salutation	Body	Closing
Signature	Sender	Recipient	

To: erik1221@cup.org

From: ingrid_soljberg@cup.org

Subject: IT'S MUM-LOOK AT THIS JOB!

Erik,

I've found a great job for you. It's in Oslo and I know you want to live there. Here's the link: www.itcomany42.org/jobs I know this company. The job is for a software engineer. They pay \$ 4150 per month!

You must have studied computer science at university, and you have to have two years' experience. It also says that you must know some Norwegian. You do not have to speak Norwegian a lot, so it's OK for you. Let me know what you think!

Love,

Mum

Appendix 7: Handout 3

Job requirements for software engineer

You must _____

You have to _____

You must know _____

You do not have to _____

Appendix 8: Handout 4

To:

From:

Subject:

I have found a job for you. It's in _____. The job is for _____. They pay _____. You must _____, and you have to _____. You must know _____. You don't have to _____.

Best wishes

Appendix 9: Model email (2)

Photography Studio Grand Opening! — ↗ ✕

To Olenna Mason ✕ Julia Fillory ✕ Henri Rousseau ✕ Cc Bcc

Photography Studio Grand Opening!

Hi Everyone,

I have exciting news for you! This Saturday will be the grand opening of my new studio, EC Photography! It will be from 10:00 to 4:00. There will be entertainment and lots of food, so come out and enjoy the festivities!

Hope to see you there!
Elena

Sans Serif ▾ | **T** ▾ | **B** *I* U A ▾ | ▾ | | | ▾

Send Saved

Appendix 10: Handout 5

Ingredients for salad:

Appendix 11: Sample text**Chicken & pesto salad**

Serves 4 Prep 10 mins

1 avocado, stoned, peeled,
finely chopped
1 small red onion, finely chopped
250g cherry tomatoes, halved
1 continental cucumber,
coarsely chopped
2 tbs Coles Basil Pesto
1 tbs lemon juice
350g Moira Mac's Classic Roasted
Chicken Breast, chopped
60g pkt Coles Australian Baby Spinach

- 1.** Combine avocado, onion, tomato and cucumber in a large bowl.
- 2.** Combine the pesto and lemon juice in a large bowl. Add half the chicken and toss to combine.
- 3.** Arrange the spinach on a serving platter. Top with chicken mixture and avocado mixture. Top with remaining chicken. Season with pepper. →

Appendix 12: Matching activity

Procedure time ingredient salad name

Chicken&pesto salad

prep 10 minutes

1 Avocado, stoned, peeled, finely chopped;
 1 small red onion, finely chopped ;
 250g cherry tomatoes, halved
 1 continental cucumber, coarsely chopped;
 2tbs coles basil pesto;
 1 tbs lemon juice;
 350g Moira Mac's classic Roasted chicken Breast, chopped;
 60 g pkt Coles Australian Baby Spinach

1. Combine avocado, onion, tomato and cucumber in a large bowl.
2. Combine the pesto and lemon juice in a large bowl. Add half the chicken and toss to combine.
3. Arrange the spinach on a serving platter. Top with chicken mixture and avocado mixture. Top with remaining chicken. Season with pepper.

Appendix 13: Handout 6

Ingredients in a bowl: _____

Ingredients on a platter: _____

Appendix 14: Handout 7

Appendix 15**FRIDAY****Chicken skewers
with easy fried rice**

Serves 4 Prep & cooking 20 mins

500g Coles RSPCA Approved Chicken
Kebabs with Thai Rub[†]
250g pkt microwavable jasmine rice
400g pkt Coles Kitchen Ready to
Stir Fry Family Mix
1 bunch coriander, leaves picked,
stems finely chopped
2 tbs Roll'd Nuoc Mam Sauce

- 1.** Heat a greased chargrill on high. Cook the skewers, turning occasionally, for 8-10 mins or until lightly charred and cooked through. Transfer to a plate. Loosely cover with foil and set aside for 5 mins to rest.
- 2.** Meanwhile, heat a large non-stick frying pan over high heat. Add the rice and stir-fry mix and cook, tossing, for 5 mins or until the vegetables are just tender. Add the coriander stem and nuoc mam sauce and toss to combine.
- 3.** Divide rice mixture among plates. Top with skewers and coriander leaves. ●